

PARLAY: A METHOD FOR CONSTRUCTING A PARAGRAPH-LEVEL NLI DATASET BASED ON MULTI-CATEGORY SCENARIOS

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This paper presents a novel methodology for constructing a diverse and comprehensive paragraph-level dataset tailored for Natural Language Inference tasks. By incorporating five scenario categories – historical events, scientific explanations, everyday situations, news reports, and fictional stories – our approach ensures broad coverage of various reasoning patterns, including transitive reasoning. The methodology employs iterative and Chain-of-Thought prompting to elicit detailed, context-rich outcomes by generating intermediate reasoning steps. Our dataset is notable for adding detailed explanations for each hypothesis, providing a valuable overview of the thought process behind each categorization. To assess the quality of these outputs, we implemented the OQACM metrics, a comprehensive framework for evaluating large language model outputs across fluency, coherence, and inference quality. This approach improves the interpretability of language models and offers detailed insights into their inferential processes, advancing NLI dataset development.

Keywords: natural language inference (NLI), paragraph-level inference, Chain-of-Thought, large language models (LLMs), LLM evaluation metrics, student paper

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Inference (NLI) tasks are crucial benchmarks for evaluating Natural Language Understanding (NLU) models, which are fundamental to various NLP applications such as question answering, translation, and dialogue (Williams et al., 2018). However, most NLI datasets and research have focused on sentence-level inference, overlooking the importance of paragraphs in discourse and text generation. Paragraphs, often described as "units of thought", go beyond the grammatical structure of individual sentences (syntax) (Zadrozny & Jensen, 1991). Analyzing how sentences within a paragraph connect through cohesion (referential links) and coherence

(logical flow of ideas) unlocks a deeper understanding of the meaning (Alyousef, 2021; Bublitz, 2011; Siddharthan, 2006). This analysis of sentence relationships is essential for tasks such as discourse, where sentences need to be arranged in a way that creates a clear and cohesive flow of information. It is essential for tasks that involve verifying the factual accuracy of summaries of documents (Yin et al., 2021). Incorporating paragraph-level semantics into NLP models could significantly improve their ability to handle real-world language tasks.

Many crowdsourced NLI datasets often fail to address real-world NLP challenges due to their creation in isolation from specific tasks and inherent annotator biases (Khot et al., 2018; Hu et al., 2020). For example, in MultiNLI, crowd workers sometimes introduced bias using specific strategies, like adding negators for contradictions, which oversimplifies the complexity of human reasoning (Hu et al., 2020). This creates an unrealistically easy task that doesn't capture the depth needed for robust NLP models. Analyses of SNLI reveal that models often rely on simple heuristics like lexical overlap, lacking compositionality in their representations (McCoy et al., 2019). High word overlap usually predicts entailment, while contradictions show minimal overlap or negation. This highlights the need for models that integrate external knowledge for more nuanced NLI tasks (Camburu et al., 2018; Dasgupta et al., 2018).

What is emerging as NLI's most pressing problem is the propensity of models to overfit on datasets. While these models perform well on training data, their generalization to unseen data is limited, a well-known issue in machine learning, and is referred to as the generalization problem (Gubelmann, 2024). An underlying cause might be the focus on deductive reasoning in training data creation. Careful examination of crowd worker instructions for popular NLI datasets reveals an emphasis on logically guaranteed inferences, neglecting inductive reasoning.

To address some of these challenges and generate more nuanced data, we propose a novel paragraph scope scenario-inference pair elicitation method in which each scenario is accompanied by multiple potential inferences. By integrating diverse reasoning modes during prompt creation, this approach aims to train an NLI model that can handle a wider range of reasoning patterns,

enhancing its robustness and generalizability.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in NLI, with a particular focus on Slovenian research, as the Parlay dataset is designed for Slovenian. Section 3 describes the Parlay dataset and its construction process. Section 4 provides a detailed analysis of the prompting techniques and demonstrates structured prompting and transitive reasoning. Section 5 evaluates the performance of GPT-4o and Gemini models using the Outcome Quality Assessment Composed Metrics (OQACM). Finally, Section 6 outlines future research directions.

2 RELATED WORK

This section reviews influential NLI datasets, focusing on cornerstone contributions and those involving reasoning beyond sentence-level, to provide context for current NLI research and lay the groundwork for subsequent sections. In addition, the development of NLI resources for underrepresented languages, such as Slovenian, is also discussed to highlight ongoing efforts in multilingual NLI.

Pioneering datasets like The Stanford Natural Language Inference (SNLI) (Bowman et al., 2015) and the Multi-Genre Natural Language Inference (MNLI) (Williams et al., 2018) set benchmarks in NLI with large-scale, balanced data and clear labels. However, over time, their limitations have become apparent.

2.1 Cornerstone and Challenging Datasets

The SNLI dataset, a cornerstone of NLI, provides a framework for modeling diverse logical relationships but is limited by sentence generation from simple static scenes, restricting reasoning diversity, and by relying on affirmative image captions, which limits the assessment of negation (Bowman et al., 2015; Hossain et al., 2020). The MNLI dataset builds on SNLI by incorporating diverse genres and domains (e.g., fiction, telephone conversations), improving robustness and supporting transfer learning (Williams et al., 2018). However, MNLI inherits SNLI's reliance on human-generated sentences and suffers from genre imbalance. Furthermore, Gururangan et al. (2018) raised concerns

that SNLI-trained models might simply exploit coincidental patterns rather than achieving genuine language comprehension.

For reasoning that goes beyond sentences, ContractNLI (Koreeda & Manning, 2021) and ConTRoL (Liu et al., 2020) are notable. ContractNLI evaluates hypotheses against entire documents, particularly contracts. The system is provided with a contract and a set of hypotheses, which could be statements about the contract's obligations, rights, or other key points, requiring models to grasp the broader document context. ConTRoL pushes boundaries in the field with reasoning at a passage level presenting challenges, beyond previous benchmarks.

2.2 Advancements in Slovenian NLI Datasets

Significant progress has been made in developing NLI resources for Slovenian, notably with the Slovene SuperGLUE benchmark and the SI-NLI dataset. The Slovene SuperGLUE benchmark (Žagar in Robnik-Šikonja, 2022) adapts the original SuperGLUE tasks to Slovenian, advancing NLU for this morphologically complex language, but it focuses on broad NLU evaluation rather than NLI specifically. The SI-NLI dataset, the first comprehensive NLI resource for Slovenian, addresses a critical gap in multilingual NLI studies by providing high-quality annotations from the Slovene reference corpus ccKres, with linguist students editing hypotheses to fit NLI relations (Klemen et al., 2024). Despite its contributions, the SI-NLI dataset faces challenges related to the manual construction of examples, which can be time-consuming and introduce biases.

The Parlay dataset differs from SI-NLI by using diverse prompting strategies to automatically generate complex examples, reducing the reliance on human-crafted data. It aims to address the challenge of higher-level reasoning beyond sentence-level NLI, allowing for deeper contextual understanding and enhancing the adaptability of the dataset to various languages and tasks. What's more, Parlay's automated methodology seeks to provide a scalable and efficient solution for NLI research, potentially complementing existing resources like SI-NLI by broadening their scope and applicability.

3 PARLAY DATASET FOR NLI

The section introduces the "Parlay" dataset, which is created to support NLI tasks across various contexts. It explains how the dataset is organized, the categories it covers and the methods used to generate scenarios and collect data.

The Parlay dataset promotes generalizability by encompassing five distinct categories for NLI tasks. To ensure further diversity, each category includes scenarios drawn from various contexts within its topic. These scenarios give brief descriptions of events or situations providing background information for the model to effectively perform different inference tasks.

The scenario categories – historical events, scientific explanations, everyday situations, news reports and fictional stories – were carefully chosen to offer a training platform for various types of reasoning. Historical events enable examination of cause and effect relationships, temporal reasoning, counterfactuals ("what if" scenarios) and analogies (Bottou et al., 2013; Pearl, 2009; Tatu & Srikanth, 2008). Scientific explanations require understanding reasoning such as *modus ponens/tollens* (Brachman & Levesque, 2004). Everyday scenarios provide a fertile environment for practical reasoning. The model may encounter incomplete information that necessitates inductive reasoning based on patterns, experiences, and common sense (Mitchell, 1997). In addition, everyday scenarios require analogical reasoning, where the model finds similarities to apply knowledge from one scenario to make sense of another (Gentner, 1983). This method helps the language model develop reasoning skills that can be useful in unfamiliar situations. News reports naturally require the model to exercise critical reasoning skills (Chen et al., 2023). Fictional stories provide a platform for exploring narrative reasoning, including understanding characters' motivations and emotions (theory of mind) (Kahneman, 2011; Reniers et al., 2011). Furthermore, because stories often involve social interactions and dynamics, the language model can learn to reason about how characters behave in social contexts and predict their actions based on social norms (social reasoning) (Paul & Frank, 2020; Wu et al., 2018).

We opted for an alternative approach to traditional methods that use natural text-based datasets, using prompt-driven scenario generation instead. Inspired by natural texts and ideas as prompt inputs, the scenarios themselves were created based on those prompts. While this approach reduces citation and authorship challenges in natural text datasets, it has limitations, including potential LLM biases similar to those introduced by human annotators in previous NLI datasets. Recognizing this, we aim to guide future research towards solutions that proactively reduce bias in generated datasets.

The dataset, constructed in Slovenian, contributes to the linguistic diversity of NLI resources, offering unique language-specific challenges and opportunities for advancing multilingual NLI models.

3.1 Dataset structure

For our NLP course project, we constructed a dataset of 100 data points, with 20 examples per category. Each category has 10 examples generated using Gemini LLM ((Google DeepMind, 2024) and 10 with GPT-4o (OpenAI, 2024). This dataset, referred to as the "Parlay dataset", serves as a starting point for familiarizing ourselves with the data collection process. However, to achieve robust results, we plan to significantly expand the dataset and develop more sophisticated prompting techniques to enhance data quality and relevance.

Our dataset, structured in JSON format, organizes relationships across five categories, with each scenario uniquely identified and classified into "Entailment", "Contradiction", and "Neutral" labels. An "OQACM Score" is provided for each scenario to evaluate its quality and relevance, supporting the selection process for both research and practical applications (refer to Section 5 for detailed methodology).

For demonstration purposes, we have selected a scenario from the historical category. The full JSON structure for this scenario can be found in our repository at the following link: https://github.com/UL-FRI-NLP-2023-2024/ul-fri-nlp-course-project-parlay/tree/main/Parlay_dataset/Results_Final_dataset/Sample_from_json

Adding explanations directly to scenario-hypothesis pairs in our NLI dataset is

a novel contribution, unlike traditional NLI datasets like SNLI and MultiNLI, which don't include explanations. Explanations, when present, are often presented in separate corpora or in studies specifically focused on explainable AI. For example, Camburu et al. (2018) introduced e-SNLI, which is an extension of SNLI with explanations added in a subsequent step rather than integrated from the outset. Similarly, other studies on explainability in NLP, such as DeYoung et al. (2020), treat explanations as an additional layer of information applied to existing datasets rather than integrating them into the core data from the beginning.

Our approach, which integrates explanations from the start, allows deeper analysis of the large language model (LLM) logic and supports "few-shot learning" by providing explicit reasoning patterns. Analyzing the explanations allows us to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying logic LLM used to establish the relationship between paragraphs. By providing explicit reasoning, the dataset supports "few-shot learning" (Parnami et al., 2022), allowing models to learn effectively even from fewer starting examples. The explanations act as a training aid, helping the LLM apply similar reasoning patterns to novel scenarios. Additionally, by analyzing the explanations, we can identify broader reasoning principles that can be applied beyond specific scenarios.

In our initial, anecdotal experiments, we noticed that prompts including explanations seemed to produce better results. While our observations were informal and not systematically tested, it appeared that the explicit reasoning in the explanations provided a clearer guide for the model, potentially leading to more accurate and coherent outputs. It seems that understanding the rationale behind each decision could help refine the model's learning process and may improve its ability to generalize from limited data.

3.2 Data collection

We developed scenarios by following specific guidelines and refining them iteratively to establish a well-controlled foundation for diverse inference pairs through prompt-driven development. For scenarios related to historical events, we drew inspiration from well-documented breakthrough events, utilizing resources such as the Wikipedia Timeline of World History and the List

of Historical Anniversaries (Wikipedia, 2024). When creating everyday life situations, we combined our creativity with generally known proverbs to develop realistic and relatable scenarios. For fictional scenarios, we relied on our imagination to craft unique and engaging narratives. For news reports, we simply provided the language model with a basic idea, and it generated the news story. Lastly, for scientific explanations, we sourced ideas from Wikipedia's List of Geological Phenomena and Timeline of Historic Inventions (Wikipedia, 2024) ensuring accuracy and relevance in the scenarios.

We employed reasoning rule-guided prompt engineering, incorporating rules like *modus ponens*, *modus tollens*, causal reasoning, textual entailment, and predictive inference (Liu et al., 2023). Prompts were crafted to integrate factual hints, guiding the model toward specific inferences (entailment, contradiction, neutral). Factual hints, pieces of information embedded in prompts, provided essential scenario knowledge and anchored the model's reasoning. While foundational, these hints alone were insufficient for real-world inferences, which required broader reasoning. To address this, we incorporated heuristics to capture general reasoning patterns, making prompts adaptable to diverse scenarios and inferences. This adaptability was achieved by exploring templates or conditional statements aligned with targeted reasoning rules.

Prompts were created and refined in English, then only the final, suitable examples were translated into Slovenian using the DeepL model (DeepL SE, 2024), followed by manual corrections. This decision stemmed from the fact that languages with fewer resources require more tokens to represent the same information. This increased tokenization could have compromised the LLM's ability to effectively simulate understanding of the concepts. English was also preferred for its extensive use in machine learning.

Another observation was that LLMs often favor short, two-sentence outputs. To address this, we implemented techniques to generate longer, more coherent paragraphs. This involved providing an example with the main idea condensed into one or two sentences, followed by explicit instructions, additional context, or question-aided expansion encouraging the model to think step-by-step, compare concepts, and elaborate in more detail, with the final option being to instruct the model to output at least 5 sentences, helping

it understand the expectation for more coherent, extended output.

4 METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodologies used to create the Parlay dataset, focusing on refining prompting techniques, applying few-shot learning, and structured prompting with transitive reasoning. The approaches were divided into two main workflows: one utilizing GPT-3.5 (OpenAI, 2023) and GPT-4o for structured prompting, and the other using the Gemini LLM with curated few-shot learning. Below is a brief overview of each workflow, followed by detailed expansions on their key technical aspects.

4.1 Refining prompting techniques using GPT-3.5

Overview

The first workflow involved refining prompting techniques with GPT-3.5 and later GPT-4o. The process included:

- Initial tests to develop an effective strategy for generating consistent NLI examples.
- Transitioning to GPT-4o for large-scale dataset creation, emphasizing structural consistency and content clarity.
- Iteratively improving prompts to address issues like correctly generating "neutral" hypotheses and ensuring the required output lengths.

Detailed Steps

Preliminary Testing with GPT-3.5:

The process began with a familiarization phase, where GPT-3.5 was introduced to the concept of NLI datasets. Initial attempts exhibited issues, particularly with generating appropriate "neutral" labels. To address this, the project member refined the prompting strategy, giving an example from the SI-NLI dataset, to guide the LLM in following the structure and reasoning required to create diverse and consistent examples across various categories. This served as a foundation for prompting GPT-3.5 to generate its own examples. The generated examples were refined to achieve a consistent

format that included the premise, hypothesis, and explanations, with a primary focus on prompting GPT-3.5 to create diverse NLI examples across various categories. On a few occasions, the project member provided prompts based on specific quotes or ideas but primarily relied on GPT-3.5's generation capabilities. A major challenge involved manually correcting examples where GPT-3.5 misinterpreted neutrality. However, some initially unclear connections between premises and hypotheses were retained when found to be logically sound upon deeper analysis.

Dataset Creation Using GPT-4o:

Following the success with GPT-3.5, the project transitioned to using GPT-4o for generating the dataset. The established structure was maintained throughout this phase by giving the LLM one of the examples from the familiarization process and asking it to create a similar example with a different topic. Prompts were refined to ensure that the generated paragraphs met the length, focusing on maintaining a five-sentence structure. Consistent output was achieved by repeatedly referencing the initial structure in subsequent prompts, allowing GPT-4o to generate coherent and structured NLI examples across various topics.

The project member chose the topic and gave it to the LLM, which then had the freedom to generate paragraphs without other limitations. An exception was made for the "News Reports" category, where the title and a source article link were provided, guiding the LLM in generating examples tied to real-world content.

4.2 Curated Few-Shot Learning with Gemini

Overview

The second workflow explored curated few-shot learning with the Gemini LLM. This approach focused on:

- Selecting well-defined data points across all five established categories.
- Employing Chain-of-Thought prompting to guide the LLM through a structured reasoning process.
- Iteratively refining prompts to improve the LLM's ability to generate logical, coherent, and insightful responses, with a particular focus on

neutral hypotheses and ensuring the required length.

Detailed Steps

Few-Shot Learning with High-Fidelity Data Points:

The process began with the careful selection of core themes for the dataset. Each theme was chosen for its potential to generate meaningful and varied NLI examples. Initial prompts were designed to lead the LLM through logical reasoning steps, helping to clarify the relationships between different elements of each data point.

Application of Chain-of-Thought Prompting and Transitive Reasoning

In this study, we enhanced inference across various contexts by employing Chain-of-Thought prompting (Wei et al., 2022) and structured prompting techniques, drawing on the dual-process theory of transitive reasoning (Wright, 2012). Chain-of-Thought prompting guided the LLM through logical steps, encouraging it to reference underlying factors and relationships in the data. This approach conditioned the LLM to infer related concepts or situations while explicitly explaining its reasoning, thereby clarifying the connections between original and inferred concepts. The method included a crucial feedback loop where initial responses were analyzed, and prompts were refined based on these analyses to improve the clarity and insightfulness of the generated explanations. This back-and-forth process ensured that the prompts became progressively more effective.

We structured the prompts to initiate transitive reasoning, facilitating the generation of intermediate steps that deepened the LLM's comprehension of the subject matter. These steps clarified relationships, connected different scenario elements, and resulted in a richer and more comprehensive set of hypotheses. This method aligns with findings by Nye et al. (2021) and Zellers et al. (2019) on breaking down complex problems into smaller parts.

Our approach was applied across five categories, each with a specific focus:

- News Reports: Extracting the core message or central theme, developing logical implications, and drawing conclusions about likely outcomes.
- Fictional Stories: Delving into character psychology by analyzing

emotions, motives, and expectations, and concluding the likely emotional or behavioral outcome.

- Historical Events: Pinpointing pivotal events, identifying cause-and-effect relationships, and concluding the broader historical impact.
- Scientific Explanations: Elucidating the main idea or phenomenon, explaining the process or mechanism involved, and concluding the significance or byproducts of the phenomenon.
- Everyday Life Situations: Focusing on common-sense reasoning by identifying the main situational factors, considering social cues, past experiences, and likely responses, then assessing the logical implications of these factors to conclude the likely outcome based on common-sense reasoning.

The prompts used for each of these categories are detailed in the provided repository: https://github.com/UL-FRI-NLP-2023-2024/ul-fri-nlp-course-project-parlay/tree/main/Working_process/second_submission/Prompt_techniques_CoT_demonstration

Addressing Challenges in Neutrality:

A significant challenge identified during this process was the LLM's interpretation of neutrality. The models often generated "neutral" hypotheses by presenting balanced opinions, juxtaposing positive and negative statements, or offering moderate viewpoints that neither supported nor opposed the main message. While this approach might seem neutral in a general sense, it did not align with the specific rationale of the NLI task, which required neutrality to involve contextually relevant statements that were not directly related to the main message. To address this, prompts were adjusted to clarify this specific interpretation of neutrality.

This refinement resulted in the inclusion of a specific prompt instruction: "The neutral hypothesis should be something mentioned in the context but not directly related to the main message and should not be made more or less likely because of the premise."

The methodology in this study shows great promise, but applying it on a larger scale brings up a few important concerns. One of the primary challenges is the

identification of high-quality, referential data points for training models using few-shot learning. This process is particularly time-intensive and requires iterative prompt refinement to optimize performance, making it labor-intensive. Furthermore, the creation of prompts for generating diverse scenarios demands careful crafting to avoid repetition, a common issue with LLMs, which tend to revert to familiar themes encountered in previous outputs. In terms of scalability, the time and cost implications of extending this methodology are not insignificant. While the initial development of prompts and LLM outputs is manageable with moderate resources, large-scale dataset creation requires considerably more effort.

4.3.1 DEMONSTRATION OF STRUCTURED PROMPTING AND TRANSITIVE INFERENCING

This section illustrates the use of structured prompting and transitive reasoning in the context of an everyday life scenario and its corresponding entailment.

1. Scenario Premise Creation:

- Identify the main idea: Organize a child's birthday party with a promised ice cream bar, but face a challenge.
- Expansion: Ice cream is unavailable due to a power outage, forcing the parent to find an alternative.

2. Entailment Hypothesis Creation:

- Identify key elements of the scenario: Main problem (no ice cream) and solution (finding alternative ingredients).
- Hypothesis and its Expansion: The parent improvises with whipping cream and cookies to create a homemade ice cream substitute.
- Reasoning: The hypothesis logically follows from the scenario.

3. Transitive Reasoning Application:

- Premises: 1. Ice cream is needed. 2. Frozen foods are unavailable. 3. The parent looks for alternatives. 4. Finds whipping cream, cookies, and milk. 5. These ingredients can substitute for ice cream.
- Connecting Premises and Conclusion: Given that the promised ice cream is not available (Premise 1 + Premise 2), the parent must find a

solution (Premise 3). They find alternative ingredients (Premise 4), which can be used to make a substitute (Premise 5).

- Conclusion: The parent ensures the party's success by improvising with a homemade ice cream substitute.

For detailed analysis, refer to the provided link: https://github.com/UL-FRI-NLP-2023-2024/ul-fri-nlp-course-project-parlay/blob/main/report/Appendices/Full_demonstration_of_transitive_inferencing.md

The integration of transitive reasoning and structured prompting significantly improved the relevance and coherence of hypotheses generated in the Parlay dataset. By providing a clear central idea and expanding it into detailed scenarios, the model is guided to focus on key aspects, ensuring logically connected and coherent hypotheses. For entailment, the main message drives the creation of hypotheses that logically follow the scenario, reinforcing the theme. In generating contradictions, the model produces texts that logically counter the main message, illustrating potential pitfalls. For neutral hypotheses, a strong grasp of the main message ensures the creation of responses that maintain neutrality without influencing the core idea.

5 LLM PERFORMANCE QUALITY EVALUATION

This section evaluates the performance of the LLMs used in this project, GPT-4o and Gemini, using the Outcome Quality Assessment Composed Metrics (OQACM).

To enhance the value of our dataset, we have incorporated a diverse array of output examples generated by two LLMs, specifically Gemini and GPT-4o. Instead of manually refining these examples to the level of grammatical correctness and clarity of inference that human editors might achieve, we opted for a different approach. Gemini outputs were more heavily refined through advanced prompting techniques, while GPT-4o outputs were selected based on their pre-existing structure, maintaining the fixed structure and length of the paragraphs that form each example. Several iterations of manual improvement were applied to enhance the quality of these outputs, though they were not taken to the standard of full human evaluation. These

enhancements were aligned with what could be achieved through advanced prompting techniques, balancing diversity and classification utility. Thus, we aimed for a dataset with higher diversity that still conveys classification value. To assess the quality of these outputs, we developed OQACM.

5.1 Outcome Quality Assessment Composed Metrics

As presented in Table 1, the OQACM outlines the metrics used to evaluate the Parlay dataset quality. This comprehensive framework evaluates LLM outputs across various categories, with a particular focus on fluency and coherence.

Table 1: OQACM Dataset quality metrics.

<i>Dataset quality</i>	<i>Weight</i>	<i>Human evaluation</i>
Fluency	2.5	
*Readability	2.5/3	1-5 scale
*Grammatical accuracy	2.5/3	1-5 scale
*Style	2.5/3	1-5 scale
Coherence	2.5	
*Completeness	0.5	1-5 scale
*Conciseness	0.5	1-5 scale
*Clarity	0.5	1-5 scale
*Organization	0.5	1-5 scale
*Focus	0.5	1-5 scale
NLI success	5	
*Entailment	1.5	1-5 scale
*Contradiction	1.5	1-5 scale
*Neutral	1.5	1-5 scale
*Explanation	0.5	1-5 scale
TOTAL OQACM (sum of grade*weight)		

Meeting these metric elements is critical for generating text that is both meaningful and engaging, ensuring high-quality LLM output. Thus, the OQACM serves as a tool to evaluate which outputs are more valuable and have greater learning potential.

The OQACM is grounded in extensive literature on the critical aspects of text

quality. Coherence is key to text comprehension, as coherent texts help form accurate mental representations (Kintsch & van Dijk, 1978). Halliday and Hasan (1976) analyze linguistic mechanisms that contribute to coherence, and McNamara and Kintsch (1996) show that coherence significantly enhances comprehension and retention. Additionally, Bamberg (1983) discusses practical criteria for evaluating textual coherence, offering a useful framework for our metrics. Fluency is crucial for discourse comprehension. Graesser et al. (2011) highlight the impact of grammatical accuracy, readability, and style on understanding. Reynolds and Schwartz (1983) show that clear examples and analogies enhance comprehension, underscoring the importance of style and readability. Snow (2010) emphasizes the importance of readability and grammatical accuracy in reading comprehension, especially within educational texts. Fluency ensures that text is grammatically correct, easy to read, and engaging, while coherence guarantees logical structure and comprehension.

"NLI success" refers to the core objective of an NLI dataset: determining whether a hypothesis is true (entailment), false (contradiction), or neutral relative to the premise. Human evaluators assess how well the paragraphs express these relations and the clarity of the reasoning ("Explanation"), with inference quality given more weight than the explanation. Inference quality ("NLI success") carries the highest weight in the OQACM, reflecting its importance relative to fluency and coherence. Fluency is weighted at 2.5/3 per category, and coherence at 0.5 per category, while each category within "NLI success" weights 1.5.

These weights play a crucial role in calculating the total score of the evaluation metrics. For each category, the evaluator's score (ranging from 1 to 5) is multiplied by the category's weight. The resulting products are then summed to produce the total score. Thus, the maximum achievable OQACM score is $12.5 + 12.5 + 25 = 50$. Conversely, the minimum possible OQACM score, calculated using the same weighted components but with the lowest scale value of 1, is $2.5 + 0.5 + 5 = 8$.

In our evaluation process, project team members score each element of the metrics on a scale from 1 to 5, guided by specific questions designed to determine the quality of the outputs.

5.2 Analysis of GPT-4O and Gemini outcomes

Our main focus was to ensure a range of examples to enhance the datasets classification effectiveness. The differences were noticeable in the complexity and diversity of inference elements, such as entailment, contradiction and neutrality across categories. Some categories featured examples with inference relationships that added depth to the dataset while others had simpler and more uniform examples following patterns like summarization or negation.

As reflected in the OQACM score, more intricate and creative examples received higher scores compared to simpler ones which although still valuable, scored lower. This intentional scoring difference highlights the nature of the dataset.

In summary, deliberate variations in complexity and diversity seen in the paragraphs generated by both models were intentionally incorporated to develop a dataset that is comprehensive, varied and effective, for classification purposes. Despite these intentional differences, our preliminary and anecdotal observations suggest that the performance of GPT-4o and Gemini in content generation is largely comparable. Both models consistently produced high-quality paragraphs. The performance of GPT-4o and Gemini was deliberately not directly compared due to the different methodologies applied in prompt refinement.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Our proposed dataset, Parlay, covers diverse situations and genres, providing a comprehensive training ground for various reasoning modes in NLI models. This diversity aims to equip models with transferable skills for novel situations and handling complex inference tasks. By providing explanations for each hypothesis, we ensure transparency in the reasoning process and enhance the dataset's value, setting a new standard for future datasets.

In the next step, we will use the dataset to train a model and see how well our approach works in real-world situations.

Manual evaluation, represented by OQACM scores, ensures high-quality

training data for LLMs and provides a standardized metric that encourages consistency in evaluation across the NLI research community. Although variations in output processing between model Gemini and GPT-4o models prevent direct comparison, we plan to standardize these processes for a more meaningful evaluation.

Future research will explore transitive reasoning in greater detail, offering intermediate steps to enhance the logical progression in hypothesis derivation.

The Parlay dataset is publicly available under the Apache License Version 2.0: <https://github.com/UL-FRI-NLP-2023-2024/ul-fri-nlp-course-project-parlay>

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PARLAY: NA SCENARIJIH OSNOVANA PODATKOVNA MNOŽICA ZA SKLEPANJE V NARAVNEM JEZIKU

S pričujočim prispevkom uvajamo inovativno metodologijo za ustvarjanje raznolike in celovite podatkovne množice, prilagojene za naloge sklepanja v naravnem jeziku (NLI). Vključitev petih različnih kategorij scenarijev – zgodovinski dogodki, znanstvene razlage, vsakodnevne situacije, novice in fikcijske zgodbe – zagotavlja široko pokritost različnih vzorcev sklepanja, vključno s tranzitivnim sklepanjem. Metodologija uporablja iterativna in na veriženju misli osnovana navodila za pridobivanje podrobnih, kontekstno bogatih rezultatov z vmesnimi koraki sklepanja. Naša podatkovna množica izstopa po vključitvi podrobnih razlag za vsako hipotezo, kar nudi dragocen vpogled v miselni proces za vsako kategorizacijo. Izpeljali smo metriko OQACM, celovit okvir za vrednotenje izhodov velikih jezikovnih modelov glede na tekočnost, koherenco in kakovost sklepanja. Ta strukturiran pristop ne le izboljšuje interpretabilnost jezikovnih modelov, ampak tudi omogoča podroben vpogled v njihove procese sklepanja, s čimer postavlja nov standard za prihodnji razvoj podatkovnih množic za naloge sklepanja v naravnem jeziku.

Ključne besede: sklepanje v naravnem jeziku, sklepanje na ravni odstavkov, veriženje misli, veliki jezikovni modeli, ocenjevanje uspešnosti LLM, študentski prispevek

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